

In search of a local development planner: Examining the professional planner.¹

1. Emmanuel M. Nyankweli, PhD

Associate Professor, Open University of Tanzania, Tanzania

Contact: emmanuel.nyankweli@gmail.com

2. Adalbertus F. Kamanzi, PhD

Senior Lecturer, University of Namibia, Namibia

Contact: akamanzi@unam.na

Abstract

The paper deals with the search for the identity of the local development searching planner. It begins by unveiling what is behind the professional discourse, the mini-rationales of knowledge, expertise, positive role in the community, and integrity, on the one hand, and its criticism based on the critical mini-rationalities of labeling, de-professionalization, governmentality, and exclusion, on the other hand. The paper proceeds by showing the context in which the planner of the current days will operate: the weakening state. The paper proposes and characterizes a searching planner as a suitable identity for a local development planner.

Keywords: planning, professional discourse, local development searching planner

¹ This publication has been revised from an article "Revamping the planning profession: from planners who mis-plan to searching planners," which was published in the *Managing Development in Africa Journal*, Volume 2 Issue 4, pp. 241-223.

1.0 Introduction

At a Refresher Course about "planning and food security,"² There was a discussion about the identity of a planner by the participants from Kenya, Uganda, and Tanzania. There were two positions in the debate. The first position argued for a professional planner whose leading role is to organize the planning process. A professional planner needs the skills related to the sequence of a planning cycle from the problem identification and analysis to the design, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation. The organization of the planning process goes hand in hand with serving the interests of the heterogeneous groups of people, and hence a need for participatory skills on the planner's side to cater to the diverse interests of the people. This planner, thus, needs to be trained because planning needs the knowledge, skills, and attitudes to be used to execute the planning tasks and responsibilities.

The second position was a critique of the professional planner. This position was based on the "Planner Vs. Searchers in foreign aid" (Easterly 2006). This writing is critical about the aid discourse in alleviating poverty, arguing that the professional planners are to blame for the thinking that aid will eliminate poverty. The paper characterizes the planners as those who produce shoddy goods consumers do not want, heavily ration such goods, provide inferior public services that satisfy no one, not to mention environmental disasters; the planners announce good intentions but do not motivate anyone to carry them out; they raise expectations, but take no responsibility for meeting them; they determine what to supply; they apply global blueprints; they think that they already know the answers and think of poverty as a technical engineering problem that their responses will solve, and as they are at the top they lack knowledge of the bottom. Such thinking about a planner is, actually, a critique of a professional planner, who is characteristically technocratic, not creative because of the inability to understand the local circumstances, and who enjoys working with blueprints.

This paper examines this dialectical positioning of the identity of a planner in order to search and unveil the tenets of the positions and suggest an identity of a planner who is suitable for local development. This search for the identity of the local development planner is guided by a critical reflection, which we anecdotally present through a paraphrase from ancient Jewish literature (Byamungu 1996). Someone was lost in the forest; he tried all ways

² This Refresher Course was organized by the Institute of Rural Development Planning (IRDP), Dodoma, and the International Institute of Social Studies (ISS), The Hague, from the 4th to the 15th of September 2017.

to get out of the woods in vain. When on the last path, which eventually was still a wrong one, he met another person and thought he was lucky because this person would tell the way out. Very disappointedly, even this person was also lost. Instead of complaining, they both decided to narrate to each other all the paths they had tried and failed so that they could push the unexplored routes. Forging an identity for a local development planner needs concerted efforts, which we do by reflecting on the professional discourse.

We begin in Section 2 by unveiling the professional discourse and its criticism. To lay out a basis to understand the context in which the planner for localized development operates, we present in Section 3 the weakening state. Finally, Section 4 offers a searching planner as a suitable identity for a local development planner.

2.0 Behind the curtains of the professional discourses

In this section, we present the professional discourse and its criticism. While the professional discourse essentializes professions, the criticism de-essentializes professions. The term discourse is used in the Foucauldian tradition, whereby reference is made to the ensemble of ideas, concepts, and categorizations that give meaning to physical and social realities (Foucault, 1995; Fairclough, 1992). In this sense, discourse becomes an underlying rationale for interpreting and understanding professions.

The professional discourse is constructed from the understanding of who a professional is. The discussion about professions was common in the 1950s and 1960s (Yee 2001; Saks 2012). For example, a traditional legal definition of a profession refers to it as "a self-selected, self-disciplined group of individuals who hold themselves out to the public as possessing a special skill derived from education and training and who are prepared to exercise that skill primarily in the interests of others" (Wright 1951). From this definition, several characteristics of professionals can be derived: they are a special group (because of their selection and discipline); they have special skills (because they are trained, and; they do professionals work for others. Greenwood (1957:46) argues that professions have a systematic theory, authority, community sanction, ethical codes, and culture as their attributes. Becker (1962:27-28) argues that for something to be a profession, it needs to be intellectual, based on knowledge and not merely routine, practical rather than academic or theoretical, its technique capable of being taught, strongly organized internally, and motivated by altruism. For Barber (1963), professions have the generalized and systematic knowledge, primary orientation to the community interest rather than to individual self-interest, self-control of behavior through codes of ethics, and; a system of rewards.

Millerson (1964) identified professions as involving a skill-based on theoretical knowledge, the skill requiring training and education, professional demonstrating competence by passing a test, the maintenance of professionalism being through integrity by adherence to a code of conduct, professional service being for the public good, and a profession being organized. For Moore (1976:5-6), the characteristics of a profession are full-time occupation; commitment to a calling; identification with peers, often in the formalized organization; possession of esoteric but useful knowledge and skills, based on specialized training or education of exceptional duration and perhaps of extraordinary difficulty; service orientation, and; autonomy.

These definitions reveal one common thing: that the professions possess some characteristics, which differentiate them from other occupations, which are non-professions. The most common constitutive elements (mini rationalities) of this professional discourse, which essentializes professions, are knowledge, expertise, a positive role in the community (Saks 2012:2), and integrity. This discourse has shaped the understanding of professions over time. This discourse clarifies who a professional planner is: knowledgeable, skilled, and a person of integrity.

The professional discourse, with its mini-rationalities of knowledge, expertise, positive role in the community, and integrity, is based on attributes, which, when subjected to criticism, unveil four critical mini-rationalities: labeling, de-professionalization, governmentality, and exclusion.

With mini-rationality labeling, a profession is viewed as a socially negotiated label based on occupational ideologies. The so-called non-professional occupations are stigmatized, and the knowledge, skills, and ethics of such stigmatized occupations are not as distinctive as supposed because they have a lot in common with the so-called professions (Brante 2012). De-professionalization is about rationalizing knowledge and expertise (McKinlay and Arches 1985) and skilled professional tasks for managerial strategies for controlling labor processes (Braverman 1974). Governmentality is about the institutionalization of expertise; so, the professions are not inherently generated by knowledge and expertise per se but rather based on the selective political incorporation of expertise into state formation as a key governance resource (Saks 2012:3; Johnson 1995). Touching upon the structure of professions, they are exclusionary social closures in the marketplace sanctioned by the state; this is necessitated by the fact of living in a dynamic and competitive world of macro-political power and interests, in which occupational groups gain and maintain professional standing based on the creation of legal boundaries that mark out the position of specific occupational groups; that is why, therefore, professionalization seeks to

attain a particular form of formal legal regulation with registers creating bodies of insiders and excluding outsiders; the professionalization is linked with the improved life chances for members of the professional group on the broader society (Saks 2003; Saks 2012).

Thus, professions are simply tags because there is nothing in professions that is substantially not found in other occupations, so-called non-professions; with so many specializations within the same professions, nothing remains solid and intact of any profession; the state institutionalizes professions for governance purposes; professions are none other than exclusionary organizations for survival. Fundamentally, the criticism to the professional discourse is that professionalism is about the ideology built around the accounts of the purpose and process of occupations, focusing on the creative knowledge and expertise of the so-called professionals (Saks 2012:3).

3.0 Weakening of the state

The criticism of the professional discourse is a decisive moment for planners in this age of strife for local development. Due to the criticisms on a professional planner, the temptation would be throwing out the baby and the water from the basin, that is, getting away with the planning profession. We still think that planners are needed, but unquestionably a different brand of planners. Before we get to the type of planner we believe is suitable for local development, we point out one critical issue for the local development planner of this particular time: the weakening of the state. This is a vital context in which the local development planner has to work.

A layer deeper in the mini-rationalities of the criticism to the professional discourse negatively impacts on the state as a dominant structure for local development. The state is being blamed for using the professionals for surveillance and control of others, for constructing professions for state governance purposes, and; for sanctioning the professions (Saks 2012).

Such blames to the state have not left the state powerful enough to run its business smoothly everywhere. With the premise of necessary participation, there has been a struggle to actualize two phenomena: political democracy and decentralized governance. Concerning democracy, the big numbers are to determine the trajectories of the states, with the incorporation of the small numbers. With decentralization, the central state gets divided systematically to promote localized governance processes. So, the oneness idea of the state is now suffering from disintegrations caused by democracy and decentralization concepts, which were once cherished, but now raising eyebrows to futurists.

The point is that a planner for local development planning no longer has a strong state that could back them up. This situation eventually leads to several questions in the planning profession: whose profession is planning? For whom do planners do their planning? With the central government in charge, the responses to such questions were straightforward: a traditional professional planner would serve to design and implement the thought plans of the central government. With the central state getting weaker, central planning is giving way to local planning for local development.

4.0 Suitable identity: local development searching planner

So, what kind of planner is needed for local development? A typical planner shaped by the professional discourse cannot work in a democratic and less centralized state, which is premised on the criticized professional discourse. We need another type of planner who can understand the changing axiologies (value systems), epistemologies (knowledge systems), ontologies (reality systems), and methodologies (inquiry systems) of the transformations in people's lives and weave them into desirable circumstances for planning for local development: the local development searching planner. Broadly speaking, the local development searching planner acknowledges the ever-changing paradigms, questions and shapes the thinking in planning in the changing paradigms. To characterize the local development searching planner more, we borrow a leaf from Easterly (2006) from his searching planner.

A searching local development planner should be able to accept responsibility for their actions, find products and public services that satisfy the people in need, find things that work and get some reward, find out what is in demand, adapt to local conditions, find out what the reality is for the people, find out if the people are satisfied, admit that they do not know the answers in advance, believe that poverty is a complicated tangle of political, social, historical, institutional, and technological factors, only hope to find answers to individual problems by trial and error experimentation, and believe that the insiders also have the knowledge to find solutions and that most solutions will be homegrown or a mixture of internal and external interventions, but seldom external interventions.

References

- Barber, B. (1963). Some problems in the sociology of professions. *Daedalus*. Vol 92(4), pp. 669-688.
- Brante, T. (2010). Professional fields and truth regimes: In search of alternative approaches. *Comparative Sociology*. Vol. 9, pp. 843-86. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/156913310X522615>
- Braverman, H. (1974). *Labor and monopoly capital: the degradation of work in the twentieth century*. New York: Monthly Review Press.
- Byamungu, G. (1996) *Stronger than death*. Reading David's rise for third millennium, Roma: Urbaniana University press.
- Easterly, W. (2006a), "Planners Vs Searchers in Foreign Aid". Paper prepared for Asian Development Bank's (ADB) Distinguished Speakers Program, Manilla, 18th January 2006.
- Fairclough, N., 1992. *Discourse and Social Change*. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Foucault, M., 1995. *Archaeology of Knowledge*. Routledge Classics, 239. <http://doi.org/10.1177/053901847000900108>
- Greenwood, E. (1957). Attributes of a profession. *Social Work*. Vol. 2 (July), pp. 45-55.
- Johnson, T. (1995). Governmentality and the institutionalization of expertise. In T. Johnson, G. Larkin and M. Saks (Eds.) *Health professions and the state in Europe* (pp. 7-24). London: Routledge.
- McKinlay, J. and Arches, J. (1985). Towards the proletarianization of physicians. *International Journal of Health Services*, 18, 161-95. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2190/JBMN-C0W6-9WFQ-Q5A6>
- Millerson, G. (1964). *The Qualifying Associations: A Study in Professionalization*. London: Routledge & Kegan Paul.
- Saks, M. (2003). The neo-Weberian approach to the sociology of the professions. In Verpraet, G, Gadea, C., Milburn, P., Vervaeke, M. and Charles, F. (Eds.). 2003. *Les professions face aux mutations internationales: les contributions récentes de la sociologie des groupes professionnels*, Paris: IRESKO/CNRS, pp. 27-41.

Saks, M. (2012). Defining a Profession: The Role of Knowledge and Expertise. *Profession and professionalism*. Vol. 2 (1), pp. 1-10.

Wright, P. (1951). *Canadian Bar Rev.* Vol. 29, pp. 748-757.

Yee, H. (2001). The concept of profession: a historical perspective based on the accounting profession in China. Presentation at the Accounting History International Conference 2001, School of Accounting and Finance Deakin University